

Assessment of the use of DNS modeling for the geometrical evaluation of variable geometry ejectors

SEMINAR – PRODEM056

Doctoral Program in Mechanical Engineering

June 2021

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Abstract

Air-conditioner (AC) devices account for 20% of overall energy consumption in buildings. Thus, there is a strong potential to effectively improve building energy performance by developing more efficient and sustainable solutions. The mechanical compressor is the main source of energy consumption. Furthermore, this equipment comprises movable parts, which increases the cost of maintenance. Reducing the compressor work is a straightforward way to decrease the energy consumption of the AC and heat-pump systems. The ejector is a simple device that can be applied to assist the mechanical compressor in a transcritical system, or to replace it completely (ejector cooling cycle) and use renewable energy, like solar heat, to drive it. Using a Variable Geometry Ejector (VGE) is the optimum choice for achieving the best performance when employing an ejector in a cooling system operating under variable conditions.

To increase ejector performance, one needs to understand the very details of the flow processes inside these devices, which is compressible, turbulent and characterized by a series of shock waves. Experimental observation of the detailed flow structure is very challenging, therefore accurate mathematical models, such as Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), have a special interest. This seminar provides a comprehensive study of state-of-art in ejector research with special attention to the different models to simulate the flow inside these devices.

Reviewing the open literature revealed that most CFD models for ejector simulations are based on different versions of the semi-empirical Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes equations (e.g. Realizable $k-\epsilon$, RNG $k-\epsilon$, or SST $k-\omega$) and assuming ideal gas behavior. The results these models show that they lack the accuracy the local flow structure inside the ejector is concerned. Considerable predicting errors are associated to the velocity and pressure profiles, shock wave location and intensity, etc. Even for global ejector performance predictions there are discrepancies between the various RANS methods.

Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) requires no model for the turbulence behavior and therefore can capture the flow physics on a fundamental level. DNS simulations however are constrained by the available computational power. Literature review shows that DNS has not been applied to ejector simulation before. This is because flows with large number of Reynolds require extremely fine space discretion to capture small eddies an alternative option is to use a hybrid approach. In a hybrid method, the flow domain is discretized using a fine mesh in regions where, e.g., DNS is used to and a coarse mesh in parts where RANS is used.

In the existing literature, there is a lack of CFD models for ejector simulations that are not based on the RANS approach. Because there is a need for fully understanding ejector operation in refrigeration systems, alternative approaches using DNS and hybrid DNS approaches should be looked at. Therefore, it is proposed in this seminar to carry out a

Ph.D. work with the principal objective to develop an alternative CFD method for ejector flow simulation, using a more fundamental approach than RANS, and to use this model to improve the performance of variable geometry ejectors.

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Abbreviations

0/1/2/3 D	0/1/2/3 Dimension
AC	Air-conditioner
CMA	Constant Mixing Area
COP	Coefficient of Performance
CPM	Constant Pressure Mixing
CRMC	Constant Rate of Momentum-Change
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DEM	Delayed Equilibrium Model
DNS	Direct Numerical Simulation
ELES	Embedded Large Eddy Simulation
FSM	Flow Simulation Method
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HEM	Homogeneous Equilibrium Model
HRM	Homogeneous Relaxation Model
LES	Large Eddy Simulation
NXP	Nozzle eXit Position
RANS	Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes
RNG	Renormalization Group
RSM	Reynolds Stress Model
SST	Shear Stress Transport
T-SST	Transition Shear Stress Transport
TFM	Two-Fluid Model

Upper-case Roman

A	Area	[m ²]
C_μ	Constant in Realizable k- ϵ model	[-]
D	Diameter	[m]
E	Energy	[J]
ER	Expansion ratio	[-]
Kn	Knudsen number	[-]
\mathcal{L}	Characteristic length of a fully turbulent flow	[m]
L	Characteristic length of large eddies	[m]
Ma	Mach number	[-]
N	Number of grids elements	[-]
Re	Reynolds number	[-]
$R\tilde{e}_{\theta t}$	Transition momentum thickness Reynolds number	[-]
S_E	External source of energy	[J]
S_M	External source of momentum	[kg.m/s]
T	Temperature	[K]
\mathfrak{S}	Transfer of energy in the energy cascade	[J]

$V_{element}$	Grid element volume	[m ³]
V_{domain}	Flow domain volume	[m ³]

Lower-case Roman

f	Arbitrary function	[-]
g	Gravity	[m/s ²]
h	Enthalpy	[J/kg]
k	Kinetic energy	[(m/s) ²]
κ	Thermal conductivity	W/(m.K)
ℓ	Eddy size	[m]
m	Mass	[kg]
\dot{m}	Mass flow rate	[kg/s]
n	Model constant in FSM	[-]
u	Velocity	[m/s]
u_τ	Friction velocity	[m/s]
p	Pressure	[Pa]
r_A	Area ratio	[-]
t	Time	[s]
x	Distance	[m]
y	Wall distance	[m]
w	Specific energy	[J/kg]

Upper-case Greek

Δx	Local grid size	[m]
Π	Ejector pressure ratio	[-]
ϕ	Arbitrary variable	[-]

Lower-case Greek

α	Constant	[-]
α_{eff}	Effective absorption coefficient	[m ⁻¹]
β	FSM coefficient	[-]
γ	Intermittency	[(m/s) ²]
δ_{ij}	Kronecker delta	[-]
ε	Kinetic energy dissipation rate	[m ² /s ³]
ε_τ	SGS energy dissipation rate	[m ² /s ³]
η	Ejector efficiency or Kologomorov length scale	[-]/[m]
λ	Entrainment ratio	[-]
λ_g	Length microscale	[m]
μ	Dynamic viscosity	[kg/(m.s)]

μ_t	Eddy viscosity	[kg/(m.s)]
ϑ	Cinematic viscosity	[m ² /s]
ρ	Density	[kg/m ³]
τ_{ij}	Turbulent shear stress	[N/m ²]
τ_{wall}	Wall shear stress	[N/m ²]
ω	Specific dissipation rate	[(m/s) ²]

Symbols and indices

ϕ_i	Value of ϕ for the inlet
ϕ_e	Value of ϕ for the outlet
$\phi_{i,j,k}$	ϕ spatial component
$\phi_{x,y,z}$	ϕ spatial component
ϕ_{sec}	Value of ϕ for the secondary flow
ϕ_{pr}	Value of ϕ for the primary flow
ϕ_{DI}	Value of ϕ for the dissipation and inertial range
ϕ_{EI}	Value of ϕ for the energy and inertial range
ϕ_{lam}	Value of ϕ for the laminar flow
ϕ_{turb}	Value of ϕ for the turbulent flow
ϕ_{out}	Value of ϕ for the ejector outlet
ϕ_{th}	Value of ϕ for the throat section
ϕ_m	Value of ϕ for the mixing section
ϕ_η	Kolmogorov scale
ϕ_0	Properties for eddies in the largest size range
ϕ_L	Properties for the large eddies
ϕ_λ	Taylor scale properties
ϕ_{path}	Mean free path
ϕ_{char}	Characteristic scale
ϕ^+	Dimensionless distance
ϕ'	Fluctuation
$\bar{\phi}$	Mean

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1 Introduction

Since the beginning of the industrial era, energy consumption in the world has shown exponential growth, as can be noted in Figure 1. It can be also noted that the predominant sources of energy are coal, oil, and gas. Using these sources of energy led to an unsustainable development of the modern world with unsustainable carbon dioxide emissions. It is now time to contradict this evolution by using renewable sources and reducing energy consumption.

Figure 1 – Global primary energy consumption by source [1].

The major part of energy consumption is for cooling and air-conditioner systems, therefore immediate actions should be taken to make them more efficient. There is an increasing need for thermal comfort, which is demonstrated by the energy consumption for air-conditioner (see Figure 2). According to the International Energy Agency [2], about 20% of the final energy in buildings is consumed by air-conditioner (AC). It was concluded that "over the next three decades, the use of ACs is set to soar, becoming one of the top drivers of global electricity demand" [2].

Figure 2 – Global air conditioner stock, 1990-2050 [2].

In the AC system, the principal energy consumer is the compressor. Additionally, this component has moving/rotating parts that increase the maintenance cost. Reducing the electricity consumption of the compressor is a logical solution to reduce the carbon emission of AC and heat-pump units. The ejector is a device that has been widely studied for expansion work recovery and to assist the mechanical compressor. An ejector has no moving parts and it is relatively simple in construction, therefore its initial and maintenance costs are low. Their application in cooling and heat pump systems has a high potential [3].

The ejector as an option for air-conditioner has been studied since the beginning of the XX century. The application in the air-conditioner of a railroad passenger car is one of the first proposals found in the literature [4]. At that time, the acquired knowledge about the ejectors was mainly empirical. At the beginning of the 40s, the first mathematical model, explaining the basis of the thermodynamic process, was presented to the scientific community [5]. The ejector flow is supersonic and highly turbulent. This complexity is still a barrier to fully understand the underlying flow physics. Once that P. Bradshaw describes “the whole phenomenon of turbulence as being unrigorous and probably invented by the Devil on the seventh day of Creation (when the Good Lord wasn't looking);” [6]. However computational power has been continuously increased and this evolution opens the door for deepening ejector analysis. The simulation of the ejector flow is now more complex and accurate. It started with a zero-dimension model and now is possible to compute a 3D model.

Yet, the simulation of turbulence is still inaccurate when the main goal is to predict local flow variables (local pressure, velocity, and density) [7]. The most common turbulence models applied to ejector simulation are based on Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) method. This is a quick and inexpensive way to predict global variables such as mass flow rates [8]. Large Eddy Simulation (LES) is a feasible solution to increase the accuracy. Nonetheless, it has some limitations, for instance, it needs a model of turbulence and specific numerical codes [9]. Direct Numeric Simulation (DNS) has been considered prohibitive due to the high computational cost [9], therefore it has not been previously applied in the ejector field.

DNS could be a fundamental tool to simulate de ejector flow, including primary stream expansion, mixing, and recompression, yet its application is constrained by the CPU of the actual computers. For high Reynolds numbers, the required mesh density is too high, leading to impractical computational cost. The complexity increases when the flow inside the ejector has two-phases. For a single-phase flow, the DNS element size is determined by the Kolmogorov scale, however, for a two-phase flow, the smallest scales have not been studied yet [10]. The mesh convergence and sensitivity need further studies. There are other aspects in a two-phase flow that are still uncertain and bring difficulty to the ejector simulation [10].

In Sections 2.1 and 2.2, the reader will find a description and classification of the different types of ejectors and their role in the cooling system. The state-of-the-art about ejector modeling and an introduction to DNS are also briefly described. This seminar work's major objective is to identify the various types of ejectors and their principal applications. Then, present the various strategies for dealing with turbulence and identify any gaps in understanding. Finally, a proposed solution to solve ejector flow turbulence is provided to accurately determine the flow's local physics.

2 Classification of ejectors and their role in cooling systems

An ejector is a device often used to compress a low-pressure fluid to a higher-pressure using heat as the energy source, without using a mechanical compressor. Ejectors can be applied, for example, in refrigeration or Rankine cycles [11]. Inside the ejector, the energy contained in a high-pressure fluid often referred to as primary flow, is used to increase the pressure of the secondary or entrained flow. The cross-section of a typical ejector is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – a) Ejector cross-section view b) idealized pressure and velocity variation in the ejector [12].

The primary flow (or motive fluid [3] – position p) passes through the throat (nozzle – position 1) expanding at a high speed (it could be at supersonic speed). This process generates a low-pressure zone at the outlet, which causes the suction necessary to move the secondary flow (suction chamber). The high difference in temperature and speed generates a boundary layer that separates the two flows, inducing high shear stresses and irreversible oblique shocks in the motive fluid [13]. This shear layer accelerates the secondary flow until it reaches a supersonic velocity and the mixing begins. The mixing process is in the constant area section (named as throat in the figure, between p_3 and p_5). After that, the fluids are conveyed to the diffuser, where the outlet pressure (p_c) is between the primary (p_p) and secondary (p_e) pressure [12]. This type of flow is complex since it is compressible and turbulent, presenting a series of shock waves. This effect is not negligible on the efficiency of the process.

This complexity increases when two phases are present in the flow [13]. In this case, the speed of sound is lower for a two-phase flow when compared with one phase. When the

primary and secondary flow rates are at their maximum, the maximum flow rate in c occurs. To have the maximum flow rate, it is necessary to have a double shock (motive flow and in 4), so, reducing the speed of sound can have an impact on the flow rate. Besides, lowering the speed of sound results in a loss of strength in the shock waves [13]. More information about ejectors with two phases flow can be found in section 2.1.2.

2.1 Classification of ejectors

There are some ways to classify ejectors including the location of the nozzle exit, the number and type of fluid phases inside the ejector, and nozzle design [11].

2.1.1 Classification according to the nozzle exit position

In ejectors, the primary nozzle exit (usually known as NXP – nozzle exit position [14]) can be located in the constant area section or the suction chamber. In the first case, it is called the constant mixing area ejector (CMA) and in the second case, it is referred to as the constant pressure mixing ejector (CPM). These two configurations are shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively. CPM configuration is the most used since it is more flexible and can operate with higher backpressures [15]. It is important to highlight that, the best geometry depends on the end application of the system.

Figure 4 – Constant mixing area ejector [15].

Figure 5 – Constant pressure mixing ejector [15].

Some authors have presented another ejector format, as Constant Rate of Momentum-Change ejector (CRMC), however, due to the complex design its use is not as widespread [16].

2.1.2 Classification according to the flow phases

Ejectors can also be classified according to the number and type of fluid phases inside them during operation. The most typical ones are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 – Different flow phases in the ejector [11].

Ejector classification		Primary flow phase	Secondary flow phase	Exit flow phase
Single-phase	Vapor jet ejector	Vapor	Vapor	Vapor
	Liquid jet ejector	Liquid	Liquid	Liquid
Two-phase	Condensing ejector	Vapor	Liquid	Liquid
	Two-phase ejector	Liquid	Vapor	Two-phase

The single face ejector is widely studied in the literature. For instance, a vapor jet ejector is a solution for subcritical air-conditioner systems [4], [14], [17], [18]. Nonetheless, the ejector flow can have two-phases and various shock waves can occur depending on flow properties [11].

The liquid jet ejector, or jet pump, is used to replace a pump, i.e. to increase a flow stream pressure [19]. A jet pump can be found in district heating and cooling systems, in the oil industry, boiling water reactors, and fish transport [19], [20]. The ejector flow has a single-phase without any shock waves [11], and the fluid properties can be approached to an incompressible fluid [19].

For the condensing ejector, the motive flow is vapor and the secondary flow phase is liquid. Due to the temperature difference, there is vapor condensation, and a liquid stream appears. There is a possibility that the stagnation pressure of this being higher than the secondary flow inlet pressure [11]. This phenomenon increases the momentum of the liquid phase. Besides, the quick condensation causes shock waves inducing a liquid state downstream of the shock [11]. The phase of the outflow is expected to be liquid in this type of system, due to the quick condensation process.

For last, the two-phase ejector has a two-phase flow in the diffuser. The primary flow is liquid, and the secondary is vapor resulting in a two-phase flow at the exit. Depending on the flow properties, shock waves may or may not occur. For instance, for supersonic two-phase ejectors, as presented in Figure 6, exist multidimensional shock wave propagation in 4. The primary flow expansion induces intensive and multiple shock waves in the mixing chamber (4) [21].

Figure 6 – Supersonic two-phase ejector cross-section view [21].

1 – primary flow entrance (liquid with subsonic velocity), 2 – primary flow diverging (supersonic velocity), 3 – secondary flow entrance (subsonic vapor), 4 – mixing chamber, 5 – constant area section, 6 – diffuser.

2.1.3 Classification of ejectors according to nozzle design

The primary nozzle design determines whether the primary flow reaches subsonic or supersonic velocity at the nozzle exit. Subsonic flow results from a convergent nozzle shape as shown in Figure 7. In this case, the Mach number (Ma) is equal to or below 1 at the nozzle exit plane. This type of primary nozzle design does not provide a significant fluid compression, which is suitable for example to exhaust gas in an industrial plant or fuel cells [22]. The flow through a convergent-divergent nozzle (see Figure 8) reaches supersonic velocities ($Ma > 1$) [11]. This design is applied in organic Rankine cycles and refrigeration systems [11].

Figure 7 - Convergent-shaped nozzle [23].

Figure 8 – Convergent-divergent shaped nozzle [23].

2.2 The ejector cooling and transcritical cooling cycles

A conventional vapor compression cooling cycle is composed of four main components: evaporator, compressor, condenser, and expansion device, as shown in Figure 9. The refrigerant (working fluid), with a low freezing point and high latent heat of evaporation, undergoes a set of thermodynamic states as it cycles through the system. The ideal properties of the working fluid in the vapor-compression refrigeration cycle is presented in Figure 10 in a p - h diagram.

Figure 9 – Vapor-compression cycle [24].

Figure 10 – Vapor-compression p - h diagram [24].

There are four distinguish the main process in the vapor-compression cycle:

- 1→2 compression, usually in a mechanical compressor. The purpose is to increase the refrigerant pressure until the condenser pressure. At that point, the fluid reaches a high temperature.
- 2→3 heat losses through a condenser at high temperatures. Is expected to condense completely the fluid reaching saturated liquid – point 3.
- 3→4 isenthalpic expansion in an expansion device. This process ends at the evaporation pressure desired, at low flow quality.
- 4→1 heat absorption in the evaporator, until complete the evaporation processes and reach saturated vapor.

The following section describes how the ejector works in a subcritical and a transcritical cooling cycle.

2.2.1 Ejector cooling cycle

The ejector in a vapor-compressor cycle can be used for expansion work recovery or as a compression device. When the ejector is applied as an expansion device, this recovers part of the expansion work otherwise lost in the cycle [25]. Figure 11 and Figure 12 represents, respectively, a schematic of a vapor-compression cycle with an ejector as an expansion device and the corresponding p-h chart. Adding an ejector in the cycle, compared with the previous one, increasing the number of processes:

- 1+2→3 expansion in the ejector. 1 is the primary flow, 2 the secondary. The outlet is a two-phase flow (3) and is conveyed to a separator.
- 3→4 there is fluid phase separation, and in 4 the fluid phase is saturated vapor.
 - 4→5 compression provided by a mechanical compressor, until the condenser pressure.
 - 5→1 heat loss through a condenser at high temperatures. As the conventional cycle, in the condenser outlet, the phase is saturated liquid – point 3. Then the flow is directed to the ejector as primary flow.
- 3→6 this stills the separator process but is the saturated liquid outcome.
 - 6→7 isenthalpic expansion is guaranteed by an expansion device, until the evaporator pressure.
 - 7→2 heat absorption in the evaporator, until complete the evaporation processes and reach saturated vapor. And enter in the ejector as secondary flow.

Figure 11 – Schematic of a cooling cycle with an ejector as an expansion device [25].

Figure 12 – p-h chart of a cooling cycle with an ejector as an expansion device [25].

For the ejector as a thermal compression device, there's no need for a mechanical compressor [3]. Figure 13 is a schematic representation of this cycle, and Figure 14 the correspondent p-h diagram. Notice that this cycle has some changes when compared with the ideal cycle (Figure 9). There are six processes:

- 1+6→2 ejector compression. The motive flow is the 6, and 1 the secondary flow. The pressure rises until the condenser pressure.
- 2→3 heat losses through a condenser, until the refrigerant becomes completely liquid – point 3.
- 3→4 isenthalpic expansion in an expansion device. This process ends at the evaporation pressure desired, at low flow quality.
 - 4→1 heat absorption in the evaporator, until complete the evaporation processes and reach superheated vapor. Is important to guarantee that 1 is superheated, to prevent a two-phase stream in the ejector.
- 3→5 pressure raised by a pump until the heat source pressure.
 - 5→6 heat absorption from a heat source, this could be renewable, as solar panels. Once, is important to obtain superheated vapor on 6.

Figure 13 – Schematic of the ejector-based chiller cycle, as a thermal compression device [13].

Figure 14 – p-h chart of a cooling cycle with an ejector as a thermal compression device [26].

In 1996, the first Variable Geometry Ejector (VGE) was presented. This ejector has a variable nozzle area (A_{th}). As a result, a better Coefficient of Performance (COP) can be achieved [17], [27]. This improvement introduces the VGE as the ideal solution to obtain the best results when the purpose is to apply an ejector as a compressor device in a cooling system.

2.2.2 Ejector transcritical cooling cycle

Using CO_2 as a working fluid has many advantages, as low Global Warming Potential (GWP), non-flammability, non-toxicity, low cost, favorable thermodynamics properties, and more compact components [8]. Nonetheless, CO_2 in a conventional vapor-compression cycle has low efficiency. Once that the critical point is at a low temperature (30.98°C), the heat rejected during the condensation is limited. To solve this problem is necessary to increase the fluid pressure beyond the critical (7.35 MPa) [28]. This increases the cycle efficiency [29].

Figure 15 and Figure 16 presents the scheme and p-h diagram, respectively, of a transcritical cooling cycle with an ejector for expansion work recovery. It has some similarities with the subcritical cycle:

- 6→1 there is fluid phase separation to saturated vapor.
- 1→3 a compressor increases the fluid pressure. Note that, in this scheme, between points 2 and 3 exists an oil separator.
- 3→5 heat losses through a condenser at high temperatures. In this cycle, the CO_2 is cooled until gathering the desired enthalpy for the ejector primary flow. Between the condenser (or gas cooler) outlet (4) and the ejector inlet (5), it is a good practice the inclusion of a control valve to minimize the fluctuations on the primary flow pressure.
- 5+8→6 expansion in the ejector. 5 is the primary flow, 8 the secondary. In the transcritical ejector, the motive fluid changes phases in the nozzle throat [29],

passing from a supercritical to liquid-vapor phase, which increases the modeling complexity. In this way, the ejector outlet (6) is a two-phase flow.

- 6→7 this stills the separator process, for the saturated liquid evolution.
- 7→8 isenthalpic expansion and heat absorption in the evaporator, until the flow evaporates completely.

Figure 15 – Schematic transcritical vapor-compressor cycle with an ejector to recover expansion work [28].

Figure 16 – p-h chart of a cooling cycle with a transcritical ejector [28].

3 Ejector modeling - the state of art

In 1858, Henri Giffard patented the injector [30] (known as jet, ejector, or jet pump [5]) as shown in Figure 17. It was used to refill the reservoir of steam engine boilers with water. The motive fluid was the steam and the secondary fluid was liquid water. Later, in 1926, Norman H. Gay proposed the first refrigeration cycle using a two-phase ejector [31]. Since then, several scientific publications were published with experimental work about the different applications for ejectors [4], [32]–[35]. Despite that, until de the '90s, the ejector operation was not fully understood [36]. In the last ten years, there has been an exponential interest in ejector technology [37], which is reflected in the number of scientific publications made in the last decade.

Figure 17 – Schematics of the Henri Giffard injector [38].

3.1 Zero/one-dimension ejector modeling

The simplest models to predict global ejector performance are referred to in the literature as zero-dimensional (0D) or one-dimensional (1D) models [39]. These models are based on the application of the conservation laws for certain characteristics (physical or theoretical) sections of the ejector. The flow irreversibility's are accounted for by using empirical coefficients which in many cases limit the accuracy of this approach [8]. The first 1D model, applied to a one-phase ejector, was presented in 1942 [40]. In 1950 Keenan et al. [5] published two theories to describe the primary and secondary flow mixing, one for the constant-pressure mixing and another one for the constant-area mixing ejector. Since then many modifications to these models were proposed [39]. The first one-dimension model developed for a two-phase ejector was established by Kornhauser in [36].

Performing a zero/one-dimension simulation of an ejector requires some assumptions that can limit the applicability of such approach [5], [39]. The most important ones are: (i) homogenous equilibrium flow, which means that the fluid is always in thermodynamic quasi-equilibrium; (ii) the mixing occurs at constant pressure or a constant area; (iii) adiabatic rigid walls; (iv) negligible kinetic at inlets and outlet; (v) uniform properties at a

given cross-section; (vi) the isentropic efficiency of the primary and secondary flow is constant, and it considers any shock that could occur; (vii) the working fluid is considered an ideal gas.

During the development of 1D models, the ejector is divided into some sections, as showed in Figure 18.

Figure 18 – Schematics diagram of ejector with the common divisions for 1D simulation [41].

There are [41]:

- Primary flow through nozzle (g);
- nozzle throat – where the primary flow chokes (t);
- Primary-flow core (from section 1–1 to section y–y);
- Secondary flow inlet (from e to section y–y);
- Cross-sectional area at section y–y;
- Cross-sectional area at section m–m, before the shock;
- Area from section m–m to section 3–3;
- Diffuser.

For each section, the following conservation laws are applied [5]:

- Conservation of mass:

$$\sum \rho_i \cdot u_i \cdot A_i = \sum \rho_e \cdot u_e \cdot A_e \quad (1)$$

- Conservation of linear momentum:

$$p_i \cdot A_i + \sum m_i \cdot u_i = p_e \cdot A_e + \sum m_e \cdot u_e \quad (2)$$

- Conservation of energy:

$$\sum m_i \cdot \left(h_i + \frac{u_i^2}{2} \right) = \sum m_e \cdot \left(h_e + \frac{u_e^2}{2} \right) \quad (3)$$

1D models are used for global ejector performance prediction or eventually to determine critical point operation or ejector geometry [42]. When a 0D/1D model is applied to an ejector is important to identify correctly all the assumptions.

3.2 Two/three-dimensional ejector models

Thermodynamic 1D models have many limitations and they are only capable to predict the global performance indicators (as entrainment ratio, critical back pressure, and flow rates). To analyze the local physics inside the ejector it is necessary to develop two/three-dimension models based on the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) method [39]. 2D models are commonly used once, in most cases, the simulated ejector can be considered axisymmetric [39]. Some authors claim the assumption of axisymmetry lead to unrealistic results, thus a 3D should be followed [8]. Because of the complexity of the problem, CFD can be used.

The governing flow equations are known as Navier-Stokes equations, there are momentum and continuity equations. it can be presented in Cartesians form as [43]:

- Conservation of mass:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho \cdot u_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (4)$$

- Conservation of momentum:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \cdot u_i)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho \cdot u_i \cdot u_j)}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + S_M \quad (5)$$

- Conservation of energy:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho \cdot E)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(u_i \cdot \rho \cdot E)}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial(p \cdot u_i)}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\kappa \cdot \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \right) + \frac{\partial(u_j \cdot \tau_{ij})}{\partial x_i} + S_E \quad (6)$$

with:

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \cdot \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \cdot \mu \cdot \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_k} \cdot \delta_{ij} \quad (7)$$

Solving those equations adds complexity to the model. Especially for a turbulent flow. To get accurate results in the best converging time, i.e. with the lower computational cost, is necessary to select the most adequate turbulence model. The reader can find more information about this in section 3.2.1.

Before the selection of the turbulence model is necessary to identify properly the boundary conditions, once that influence the flow properties, like pressure, temperature, and velocity. Boundary conditions are the flow involving properties, as inlet, outlet, and walls.

- **Wall**

To define correctly a wall is necessary to take into account the details in Table 2, where are presented the typical conditions for the ejector [44], [45]. These conditions do not depend on the flow characteristics or the ejector application.

Table 2 – Ejector modeling wall boundary condition details.

Shear condition	No-slip condition
Wall roughness	Usually is applied the Law of the wall (more information on page 22)
Flow velocity near the wall	$u = 0 \text{ m/s}$
Thermal boundary conditions	The walls are assumed as adiabatic

- **Inlet**

For the primary and secondary flow in the ejector (the inlets) the boundary conditions depend on the ejector application. For the ejector in a cooling cycle, usually, the boundary conditions depend on the condenser, evaporator, or heat source pressure and temperature.

- **Outlet**

The outlet pressure will be defined by the ejector geometry and operation curve (for more information read page 28). This reminds the importance of design the ejector considering the application of this, to obtain the expected outlet properties.

3.2.1 Turbulence models

The Reynolds number (Re) is defined as the ratio between two terms of Newton law of the movement in a flow: the momentum and viscous force [46]:

$$Re = \frac{\rho \cdot u \cdot D}{\mu} \quad (8)$$

The flow is laminar when the Re is low since the viscous forces are high enough to absorb the fluctuations that are produced by the inertial. However, when the inertial forces increase the flows become chaotic, the velocity and pressure change randomly [43], [46], the flow becomes turbulent. Figure 19 shows the difference between laminar and turbulent flow, it is possible to observe the chaos in a turbulent flow. The laminar flow streamlines are parallels to each other, with soft changes of direction. On the other hand, the turbulent flow is typified by rotational flow structures called eddies, which do not exist

in laminar flow. Ejectors are characterized by high flow velocities and Re numbers, thus turbulence must be properly tackled in their mathematical models.

Figure 19 – A laminar (yellow and green) and turbulent (blue) flow scheme [47].

To determine the physical phenomena in a complex flow it is important to calculate the shear stress and the velocity profile. The global shear stress (τ) can be decomposed into laminar (τ_{lam}) and turbulent components (τ_{turb}) as:

$$\tau = \tau_{lam} + \tau_{turb} \quad (9)$$

In equation (9) the laminar flow shear stress is defined as:

$$\tau_{lam} = \mu \cdot \frac{d\bar{u}}{dx} \quad (10)$$

The shear stress depends on the velocity profile. To find a suitable mathematical description for the flow field, it is important to understand the flow structure of a fully developed turbulent flow.

There are many different models in the literature to tackle turbulent flow. Several of them have the same basis, however, they were developed to describe better some of the flow specifics, depending on the application [48]. The choice between the turbulence models for flow simulation depends, besides other factors, on whether it is necessary to resolve large and/or small eddies. RANS, LES, and DNS models approach the mathematical description of turbulence in different ways. RANS models turbulence using a semi-empirical method without resolving large or small-scale eddies. When large eddies are of interest, LES can be applied. Out of the three approaches, only the DNS method is suitable to describe turbulence fundamentally and resolve the eddies at all scales. Figure 20 is a resume scheme about the difference between them.

Figure 20 – Comparison of RANS, LES, and DNS methods for turbulence modeling.

The optimal choice between the different approaches depends on the goal of the simulation and the flow characteristics. Some authors presented hybrid solutions, where the most detailed model is applied to the critical regions of the flow domain [47]–[49]. This reduces the computational cost with some loss of information that is considered to be less relevant for the analysis. There are several flows with high scientific interest [6], as the flow inside an ejector, that are difficult to study using experimental methods and for better understanding the physics, DNS would provide a meaningful contribution.

3.2.1.1 Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS)

A laminar flow can be fully described by the Navier-Stokes equations. However, a turbulent flow has fluctuations that have a strong impact on the wall shear stress [46]. The randomness nature of turbulence makes it difficult to describe the flow properties in an easy way. One approach is based on the Reynolds decomposition method [43]. Figure 21 is the graphic representation of the Reynolds decomposition, for the velocity. The different terms of the flow properties can be decomposed into a time-averaged (for example: \bar{u} , \bar{v} , \bar{p}) and fluctuating term (u' , v' , p') as:

$$u = \bar{u} + u' \quad (11)$$

Where the mean flow property, as velocity is defined as following [43]:

$$\bar{u} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_0^{\Delta t} u(t) dt \quad (12)$$

And the time average for fluctuations is [43]:

$$\bar{u'} = \frac{1}{\Delta t} \int_0^{\Delta t} u'(t) dt \equiv 0 \quad (13)$$

Figure 21 – Velocity fluctuation in a turbulent flow – Reynolds decomposition.

RANS applies the Navier-Stokes equations in a Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) , through that, a new term appears, that is known as Reynolds Shear Stress [43]:

$$\tau_{ij} = -\rho \cdot \overline{u'_i \cdot u'_j} \quad (14)$$

And, in the end, the RANS equations are very similar to the Navier-Stokes equation previously presented in equations (4), (5), (6) [50], [51]. Nonetheless, the turbulent shear stress, defined in (7), is simplified by the Boussinesq eddy-viscosity approximation. It assumes that the Reynolds stress is proportional to mean rate deformation [43]:

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu_t \cdot \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \cdot \rho \cdot k \cdot \delta_{ij} \quad (15)$$

Where μ_t is the eddy viscosity and δ_{ij} is the Kronecker delta ($\delta_{ij} = 1$ if $i = j$ and $\delta_{ij} = 0$ if $i \neq j$) [43].

The isotropic turbulent kinetic energy per unit mass is defined as:

$$k = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\overline{u_x'^2} + \overline{u_y'^2} + \overline{u_z'^2} \right) \quad (16)$$

This simplification was never verified through experimental data and numerical databases, this is expected to introduce some level of error to the results [52].

The normal shear stress is defined by:

$$\tau_{ii} = -\rho \cdot \overline{u_i'^2} \quad (17)$$

For the Navier-Stokes equations, even with the Boussinesq hypotheses, there are more unknowns than equations, therefore it is necessary to include more equations to close the system. These new equations, and the quantity of, depending on the turbulence model selected. A diagram with the classification of existing turbulence models is presented in Figure 22.

Figure 22 – Classification of turbulence models in CFD analysis.

Each model in Figure 22 was developed to resolve some particularity from a specific flow. More specific characteristics of the models are mentioned below.

- 1 equation model:
 - Spalart-Allmaras turbulence model [43] is a one equation model that resolves a transport equation for the kinematic eddy viscosity (μ_t). This model was first developed for low Reynolds Number turbulence and wall bounded flow [44] and it requires very fine meshes [53]. More information about this model can be found in [43].
- 2 equation models
 - The k-ε model considers a scalar transport equation for the turbulence kinetic energy (k) and another for dissipation rate (ε) [43]:

$$\varepsilon = \rho \cdot C_\mu \cdot \frac{k^2}{\mu_t} \quad (18)$$

Where C_μ is a model constant, this value depends on the k-ε model used [54]. This model was developed for fully turbulent flows and neglects the molecular viscosity effects.

- The Standard version of this model fully describes the mechanisms of turbulent kinetic energy [43], however, it is not adequate for flows with high local acceleration [7]. Some modifications were made to

the standard model to improve prediction accuracy for a wider range of turbulent flows. In [43] all the model equations are completely defined.

- ReNormalization Group k - ϵ , known as RNG k - ϵ , is similar to the standard model, a mathematical technique called renormalization is applied to reduce computational effort [44], [55]. It is ideal for predict the center line pressure [7]. Bartosiewicz *et al* [55] describe the mathematic model in detail.
- The Realizable k - ϵ model has more accuracy than the previous models for the turbulence kinetic energy calculation [56]. In this model the term C_μ is determined using the Schwartz inequality for turbulent shear stress [54]. This model predicts with accurately the primary fluid expansion after the nozzle outlet [7]. However, this model may require longer computational times than the rest of the k - ϵ models.
- The k - ω turbulence model was developed to improve the results near the wall, once that this does not need wall functions. In k - ω models, the turbulence kinetic energy (k) and the specific dissipation rate (ω) are computed. Near the wall, k is set to zero and ω to infinite, or a very large number [43]. The great advantage is that the experimental work showed that, the near-wall values are not relevant to obtain precise results [43]. More information about these models can be found in [43].
 - The standard k - ω shows good results for the boundary layer limit, even for flow with high-pressure gradients [55].
 - The Shear Stress Transport (SST) k - ω model combines the advantages of the k - ϵ and k - ω models. It predicts with the best accuracy global and local flow parameters for one-phase flows [8]. This model includes an additional cross-diffusion term for ω , to ensure that the models lead to accurate results for both the near-wall and far-field zones [44]. It is also more suitable for cases with adverse pressure gradient flows [44], [54].
- 4 equation model
 - The Transition Shear Stress Transport (T-SST) model combines k - ϵ and k - ω models. The standard k - ω model is the basis. Two additional scalar transport equations are added to the system of equations including a transport equation for the intermittency (γ) and another for the transition momentum thickness Reynolds number (Re_{θ_t}) [44]. Besides all the advantages of the standard k - ω model, the T-SST model describes with precision the transition flow region near boundaries or free jets [7].

- 5 equation model
 - Reynolds Stress Model (RSM) resolves the RANS equations without applying the Boussinesq hypothesis [51]. Instead, it solves transport equations for the Reynolds stresses and a dissipation rate equation. This is a most complex model, once this takes into account all the Reynolds Stress components [57]. However, the model validity is limited by the underlying assumptions. Ejector flow simulation using RSM could lead to numerical convergence problems and time-consuming computation [53].

Table 3 summarizes some selected published model validation works with experimental data. Looking at the table, one may see that most of these validation works considered different turbulent models for simulating the same ejector and the different authors considered different working fluids.

Table 3 – Some conclusions about turbulence models on ejector vs experimental results. The ✓ corresponds to the models simulated by the authors and ✓ the best result when compared with experimental data.

Paper reference	Turbulence model							fluid	
	Standard k-ε	Realizable-k-ε	RNG k-ε	Standard k-ω	SST k-ω	SST k-ε	T SST		RSM
[55]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓	Air
[58]	✓				✓				
[59]	✓	✓	✓						H ₂ O
[7]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		
[60]		✓	✓			✓			R141b
[61]	✓		✓		✓				R134a
[62]	✓	✓	✓						

Considering air as a working fluid, for a one-phase supersonic ejector, Bartosiewicz et al. [55] concluded that RNG k-ε and SST k-ω are the bests to predict the shocks localization and its strength, as well as the mean line of pressure recovery. However, using the turbulent model SST k-ω stands out because it has resulted in the lowest simulation error for the stream mixing process. In contrast, Hemidi et al. [58] found that, compared with SST k-ω, for one phase flow, Standard k-ε shows the best overall results, especially in design conditions. It is important to highlight that for both models, the entrainment ratio (more information about this performance indicator can be found on page 28) was the same. Nonetheless, the local flow structures were very different.

Yang et al. [59] compared the three k-ε models previously presented in a steam ejector. The authors assumed a saturated state of booth, primary and secondary flow. The Realizable k-ε had accurate results for the static pressure profile along with the ejector and the entrainment ratio. Considering the same fluid, water, Varga et al. [7] obtained different results. They compared the results of an ejector working in a cooling system. The

SST model had a lower error (for the COP and critical back pressure) when compared with the others models. However, the authors noticed that modifying the Standard $k-\epsilon$ constants improves the accuracy of the model. They used constants that were found on the literature that were obtained by experimental work, even for different ejector geometry and working fluids.

For a one-phase ejector with R141b as the working fluid, Zhu et al [60] concluded that the RNG $k-$ model has the best accuracy in predicting the ejector entrainment ratio when compared with Realizable $k-\epsilon$ and SST $k-\omega$.

For R134a, two papers were analyzed. The first, from Lin et al. [61], concluded that for a one-phase ejector, the SST $k-\omega$ had the most accurate results for primary and secondary flow prediction. For the same fluid, Yan et al. [62] concluded that the Standard $k-\epsilon$ approach had the best results when the model constants were calibrated by experimental data. That conclusions is the same that was presented by Varga et al. [7].

This discrepancy regarding the performance of the different turbulence models is frequent. There is no single method that applies to ejector flow simulation with the highest accuracy. Model performance depends on ejector geometry, boundary conditions, and fluid properties [15]. There are RANS models that can predict global ejector performance (as entrainment ratio), but this does not guarantee a precise forecast of the local flow physics (as velocity, pressure, shock waves location, and others) [58].

According to the model chosen to tackle turbulence, it may be necessary to resolve the near-wall region separately. There are two methods: the *wall function law*, and the *near-wall model approach*. Figure 23 shows a scheme with the difference between both methods. The near-wall model extends the turbulence model until the wall and resolves completely all the flow [50].

Figure 23 – Wall function vs near-wall model [44].

On other hand, the *wall function law* does not describe accurately the near-wall region. Instead, this method assumes that the total shear stress (defined in equation (9)) is equal to the wall shear stress (τ_{wall}) [50].

To understand what is the wall shear stress first is necessary to analyze the 1D velocity distribution profile near a wall boundary (boundary layer). This is shown in Figure 24. According to the figure, in the boundary layer, one may distinguish three different flow regimes (layers). The first layer, nearest to the wall, is called the *viscous wall layer*. In this layer the flow is laminar and the velocity profile is almost linear with the velocity gradient constant equal to u/y [63]. Consequentially, applying the equation (10), the shear stress at the wall becomes:

$$\tau_{wall} = \frac{\mu \cdot u}{y} = \frac{\vartheta \cdot \rho \cdot u}{y} \quad (19)$$

In equation (19) y represents the wall distance.

Figure 24 – Typical velocity distributions in turbulent flow near-wall [64].

In the viscous layer, the wall shear stress can be rewritten as a function of the shear velocity or friction velocity (u_τ) as:

$$u_\tau = \sqrt{\frac{\tau_{wall}}{\rho}} \quad (20)$$

Replacing τ_{wall} , in equation (19), by the shear velocity it is possible to obtain the relation between the characteristic near-wall flow velocity (u^+) and the dimensionless distance from the wall (y^+) [50]:

$$\frac{y \cdot u_\tau}{\vartheta} = \frac{u}{u_\tau} \quad (21)$$

Where the dimensionless distance from the wall is equal to [43]:

$$y^+ = \frac{y \cdot u_\tau}{\vartheta} \quad (22)$$

and the characteristics velocity:

$$u^+ = \frac{u}{u_\tau} \quad (23)$$

In the Overlap Layer and Outer Turbulent Layer in Figure 24, the dimensionless velocity is a function of the dimensionless distance from the wall. This function was obtained experimentally for a plane channel, a circular section pipe, and a flat plate as depicted in Figure 25. The buffer layer and the log-law region are subdivisions for the overlap layer in Figure 24.

Figure 25 – Normalized velocity profile and wall distance for a plane channel, a cross-section circular pipe, and the boundary layer on a flat plate [50].

Equation (10) is only valid in the viscous wall layer (or viscous sublayer), starting near the wall until $y^+ = 5$. The *buffer layer* (or blending region ($5 < y^+ < 30$)) is the section where the *law of the wall* overlaps the *log-law region*. Both experimental data and direct numerical simulation (DNS) confirmed the *logarithmic law* (valid on the log-law region for $y^+ > 30$) [50], [57], [64] which is written as:

$$u^+ = 2.4 \cdot \ln(y^+) + 5.21 \quad (24)$$

Recent investigations concluded that the *logarithmic law* is not universal, some variations depend on Reynolds number and flow domain [50]. Thus, it is important to determine the constants in equation (24) for a specific problem [57]. Note that the *buffer layer* does not provide a direct relationship between u^+ and y^+ , therefore equation (22) is applied for $y^+ \leq 11.63$ while equation (24) for $y^+ > 11.63$ [43].

The y^+ value is used in CFD to set mesh density near the wall region for accurate prediction of the flow in the boundary layer [57]. The recommend value is $y^+ > 30$, this conduces to a lower computational effort. Figure 26 shows the reason, once that, for y^+ higher than 30, the variation of normalized production (P_k^+) and dissipation of turbulent kinetic energy (ε^+) are similar, assuming that the flow is in equilibrium and $P_k = \varepsilon$ [50]. Where it can be observed in the following equations [50]:

$$P_k = \tau_{wall} \cdot \frac{\partial \bar{v}_t}{\partial y} \quad (25)$$

$$\varepsilon = \vartheta \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^2 k}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (26)$$

Being y the wall distance. This assumption is the base for the *wall function* presented by Launder and Spalding [65].

Figure 26 – Variation of normalized production and dissipation of turbulent kinetic energy across boundary layer in a plane channel, a pipe, and a flat plate boundary layer flow [50].

3.2.1.2 Large Eddy Simulation (LES)

The chaos in a turbulent flow is characterized by eddies with different lengths and time scales. The RANS models are used to describe all eddies by a single turbulence model, however, the energy exchange between eddies is an obstacle in the selection of the most appropriate model. For high Reynolds numbers, the smaller eddies can be approached to isotropic and are considered as having a universal behavior. The largest eddy's characteristics depend on the flow domain, boundary conditions, and body forces. Dissimilar to the small eddies, the big eddies are anisotropic and interact/extract energy from the mean flow [43].

LES was developed to resolve completely the large eddies and treat the small eddies as means of a sub-grid scale model [43], [44]. LES is a bridge between DNS and RANS, once that's DNS resolves all the flow. LES requires a much coarser mesh than DNS, however, comparing with RANS models, LES needs a substantially finer mesh. Besides that, for transient models, LES needs a long flow time to converge.

The use of LES for ejector flow modeling is not common, only some recent publications are available. Medeiros et al. applied LES to a one-phase water ejector simulation [66].

The authors found a different behavior in the experimental Mach number profile when compared with LES data. The difference was due to the temporal averages used in the simulation. For the pressure profile determined by LES, this was very similar to the one obtained by the SST $k-\omega$ model.

Zaheer and Masud [48] applied a hybrid approach, LES for the mixing section, and RANS for the remaining parts of the one-phase ejector, with water as a working fluid. The outlet mass flow rates were compared with experimental data, for three different primary inlet pressures (with the same secondary inlet pressure), obtaining a maximum error of 1.9%. However, local flow variables were not analyzed.

For a transcritical R744 ejector, Fang and Poncet [67] developed an LES model using a density-based solver. The authors concluded that the model accuracy to predict the pressure distribution is related to the nozzle geometry. Besides, the results need to be validated with more experimental data including mass flow rate, velocity, and density gradient.

3.2.1.3 Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS)

Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) computes the flow at all scales, by solving the Navier-Stokes equations and without applying any model describing the turbulence. DNS also has a transient nature, characterized by very small time steps and by a fine numerical mesh, with element size small enough to resolve the small-scale turbulent eddies and temporal fluctuations [43]. The major disadvantage of DNS is the high computational cost involved that is proportional with the flow Reynolds number [43], [44]. Chapter 4 in the present seminar is dedicated to present the DNS method in more detail.

3.3 Multiphase models

Multiphase models must solve the governing equation for the multiphase flow and track the equilibrium between the different phases according to some predefined assumption. The most commonly used models are:

- **The homogeneous Equilibrium Model (HEM)** assumes the thermodynamic equilibrium of the phases is assumed at all the points, where the thermodynamic state is defined by pressure and enthalpy [8]. The temperature and pressure of both phases are considered to be the same. This model also assumes that the phases are perfectly mixed, meaning that they have the same velocity and are in mechanical equilibrium [68].
- **The homogeneous relaxation model (HRM)** considers a relaxation process towards the thermodynamic equilibrium of the phases, by introducing a finite relaxation time [69]. This model uses empirical values to set the relaxation time, which leads to a need to adapt the model to each ejector.

- **The mixture model** has several variants, nonetheless, in all of them, the thermodynamic properties of the mixture are calculated by a mass-weighted average of each phase [8]. Compared with HEM, this model shows a smooth variation of fluid density. Therefore, the mixture model predicts with less error the entrainment ratio and the motive mass flow rate [70]. However, Giacomelli et al. [70] concluded that the convergence time was ten times higher when compared to the HEM scheme. Recent mixture models predicted the primary mass flow rate within a 2% error [70]. However, this error increased for lower primary flow pressures [8].
- **The delayed Equilibrium Model (DEM)** assumes that the flow is represented by phases: saturated vapor, saturated liquid, and metastable liquid. It considers a pressure equilibrium between all the phases but with a thermal non-equilibrium, where the metastable liquid has a higher temperature than that of the saturated liquid and vapor [8].
- **The two-fluid model (TFM)** has only been recently used for ejector simulation [8]. It treats each phase separately [71], in other words, these models add two sets of the previously presented equations ((4), (5), and (6)) and an interface model between them [8]. It is important to note that the phases are not independent, so this model includes interaction terms between the phases. Non-equilibrium between phases is considered by using a momentum equation for each phase and independent velocity vectors [71].

There are four major properties to evaluate when non-equilibrium between phases is considered: pressure (often neglected in most models), velocity, temperature (can be neglected if the mesh has a resolution that allows to each cell contain only one phase), and chemical potential. Only the mixture model and TFM allows the application of the non-equilibrium momentum in which case each phase has its velocity field. However, other models can take into account the velocity split (i.e., velocity non-equilibrium) adding an extra equation for velocity slip between the phases [72]. It is noted that most of the velocity split models only consider drag forces between phases, neglecting all the other interactions [8]. Another detail is that it is necessary to estimate the relaxation time for the velocity [8]. Despite all the effort, it was concluded that considering the momentum non-equilibrium had only a minor effect on the ejector global performance.

It is important to highlight that none of the presented models can predict accurately the secondary mass flow rate. Typical errors are higher than 20% [8]. This happens because this flow rate is directly dependent on the motive flow rate, the turbulence of the mixing, local velocity vector, and multiphase momentum interaction [8]. On the other hand, the motive mass flow rate depends on primary flow pressure and temperature, which leads to more accurate results.

Summarizing the results of the literature review: it can be concluded that HEM provides accurate simulations at supercritical conditions, however, it fails when the ejector works

at low pressure in the primary flow. The HRM provides better results when applied three zones for the relaxation time description. The mixture model needs validation for sub-critical conditions, once that this model has not been tested under these conditions. This model and TFM translate in a realistic way the physics behind the multiphase flow, nonetheless more studies are needed for validation for the ejector working in the sub-critical range.

3.4 Measuring ejector performance

The ejector operational characteristics are measured with three metrics, the main is known as entrainment ratio, and is considered as the ejector performance indicator [58]. The entrainment ratio is the fraction between the secondary flow mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{sec}) and the primary flow mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{pr}) [17]:

$$\lambda = \frac{\dot{m}_{sec}}{\dot{m}_{pr}} \quad (27)$$

The operating curve of the supersonic ejectors, presented in Figure 27, describes the relationship between the entrainment ratio and the backpressure, under constant inlet conditions. It can be seen from the figure that a supersonic ejector can work in two different regimes: double choking and single choking. A sonic ejector only works in a single choking regime. The back-flow regime corresponds to the ejector failure. The critical point of operation occurs at the maximum backpressure (critical pressure) to the maximum entrainment ratio.

Figure 27 – Ejector operation regimes.

For a given inlet condition, the motive fluid mass flow is constant because of the choking in the nozzle throat. When the ejector work in the double choking regime, the secondary stream also reaches $Ma=1$, thus the flow becomes independent of the downstream pressure. However, by increasing the backpressure above the critical point, the secondary flow remains subsonic, thus its flow rate depends on the pressure difference between the inlet and outlet, and its value is always inferior to the one observed during choked

conditions. Further increase of the backpressure reduces the secondary flow rate to zero or eventually backflow in the suction chamber occurs (backflow regime) [73].

Besides the back pressure, the NXP (nozzle exit position) influences the entrainment ratio. The primary and secondary flow only start mixing when the secondary reaches sonic velocity, until that the primary jet expansion, after the nozzle, creates a separation layer between the flows, as shown in Figure 28, reducing the secondary effective flow area [15]. This phenomenon has an impact on the secondary flow rate.

Figure 28 – Motive flow expansion after the nozzle and impact in the secondary flow [15].

The other two operational characteristics of the ejector are the compression ratio [37]:

$$\Pi = \frac{p_{out}}{p_{sec}} \quad (28)$$

And the expansion ratio [73]:

$$ER = \frac{p_{pr}}{p_{sec}} \quad (29)$$

Yet, there is the ratio between the throat section area (A_{th}) and the constant area mixing section area (A_m) [74]:

$$r_A = \frac{A_{th}}{A_m} \quad (30)$$

The VGE is a solution to change the r_A , once that it is possible to add a spindle in the nozzle that varies the throat section area (A_{th}) [14]. Ideally, an ejector should operate with a high entrainment ratio and pressure ratio simultaneously. However, the coupled optimal value is difficult to achieve.

ASHRAE [13] proposed a definition for the ejector efficiency as the ratio between the actual compression energy recovered, and the theoretical energy available in the motive stream:

$$\eta = \frac{(h_{out} - h_{sec}) \cdot (\dot{m}_{pr} + \dot{m}_{sec})}{\dot{m}_{pr} \cdot (h_{pr} - h_{sec})} \quad (31)$$

An alternative definition for the ejector efficiency was proposed by Stefan and Pega [75] by evaluating the following formula:

$$\eta = \lambda \cdot \frac{h(p_{out}; s_{sec}) - h_{sec}}{h_{pr} - h(p_{out}; s_{pr})} \quad (32)$$

Equation (32) relates the ejector work recovery to the ejector work recovery potential, or in other words the isentropic compression work to the maximum work that the ejector could recover with the motive flow [75].

Carrillo et al. [76] proposed a new definition of ejector efficiency:

$$\eta = \frac{\Delta p}{\Delta p'} = \frac{p(h_{out}; s_{out}) - p_{sec}}{p(h_{out}; s_{sec}) - p_{sec}} \quad (33)$$

This approach defines the ejector efficiency as a ratio between the pressure increase in the ejector (secondary stream to outlet) and the isentropic pressure increase. It is important to highlight that each efficiency definition (equation (31) to (33)) results in different values for different fluids. For example, for a high-operating pressure refrigerant such as CO₂, the typical work recovery efficiency is about 20-30% (which one if gives a different value). For a subcritical ejector, the efficiency is usually less than 20%. Experimental work [37] demonstrated that the highest cooling efficiency operation does not necessarily coincide with the highest ejector efficiency. The ideal ejector design should take into account both ejector and cooling cycle efficiencies (COP) [37]. Where the cooling efficiencies for the two different cooling cycles with ejectors are written as following:

- For cooling system with an ejector as an expansion device [25]:

$$\text{COP} = \lambda \cdot \frac{\Delta h_{evap}}{\Delta h_{comp}} \quad (34)$$

- For cooling system with an ejector as a thermal compression [77]:

$$\text{COP} = \lambda \cdot \frac{\Delta h_{evap}}{\Delta h_{heat}} \quad (35)$$

4 DNS simulation of complex flow phenomena

DNS simulations applied to turbulence flows is relatively *recent*, since it requires high computational effort. The computational effort is translated into a long time to obtain a solution, which becomes impractical in cases where a large number of simulations are needed. Figure 29 is a simple scheme to show the parallel between simulation duration for the different approaches. Note that it is difficult to predict if hybrid simulation, as LES/RANS or DNS/LES, will take more computational work than LES, or not. However, it will likely depend on how much of the flow domain is RANS/LES/DNS and the interface methodology used.

Figure 29 – Schematic representation of the time taken to solve a turbulent flow with different 2D and 3D approaches, where the smaller area represents the lower computational cost.

Figure 30 shows the impact of the computational cost on the simulation outcomes. This figure represents a comparison of the results for an atomizing liquid jet using the DNS (left) and LES (right) simulations. The DNS picture clearly shows both the droplet of the atomized liquid and the instability waves formed on the jet. In this, it is possible to see what happens when the small eddies are modeled (LES) instead of solved (DNS) [78], once that for LES the small scale is not visible.

Figure 30 – Atomizing liquid jet results using DNS (left) and LES (right) [78].

4.1 Turbulence modeling using DNS

Existing turbulence models were briefly explained in Section 3. Turbulence is a continuum phenomenon, therefore the Navier-Stokes equations are valid. Main flow, large and small eddies are all described by this set of equations [6], [79]. Any type of flow could be calculated if a general solution existed. [6].

The energy cascade is one of the main reasons for high turbulent flow complexity. This phenomenon occurs due to eddies instability. This causes them to break up and transfer the energy, mass, and momentum to smaller eddies. This process is repeated until the eddy motion is steady and the molecular viscosity can dissipate the kinetic energy [80]. A turbulent flow is characterized by eddies of varying lengths (ℓ), where ℓ upper limit is limited by flow geometry and the lower limit is determined by the diffuse action of molecular viscosity. Due to geometry dependence, the larger eddies are assumed to be anisotropic and predictable. On the other hand, for smaller eddies, the vortices follow a more random behavior, so it is assumed as isotropic [79].

Kolmogorov proposed a hypothesis for establishing anisotropic and isotropic length scales for eddies [80]. Assuming that the eddies in the largest size range are characterized by the length scale ℓ_0 , Kolmogorov's hypothesis of local isotropy assumes that the eddies are considered as anisotropic (energy-containing range) when:

$$\ell > \frac{\ell_0}{6} \quad (36)$$

and isotropic (universal equilibrium range) for:

$$\ell < \ell_0/6 \quad (37)$$

With:

$$\ell_0/6 \approx \ell_{EI} \quad (38)$$

Where EI refers to Energy and Inertial ranges [80].

Figure 31 describes the different ranges and length scales for the eddies size. The energy-containing range (Energy and Inertial range – EI) is for all the eddies larger than ℓ_{EI} (defined in equation (38)), and the maximum size is limited by the characteristic length of the fully developed turbulent flow (\mathcal{L}). The universal equilibrium range is divided into two: the inertial subrange and the dissipations range. The interface between them is defined by ℓ_{DI} .

Figure 31 – Different ranges and length scales of eddy sizes at very high Reynolds number [80].

For scales within the universal equilibrium range, Kolmogorov presented the first similarity hypothesis, where the statistics (length scale η , velocity scale u_η and time scale τ_η) have a universal form determined by dissipation rate (ε) and cinematic viscosity (ϑ) [80]. These statistics are known as the Kolmogorov scales, and it represents the smaller length possible in turbulence and it is proportional to the grid spacing in the mesh. Those and are defined as:

- Length scale:

$$\eta = \left(\frac{\vartheta^3}{\varepsilon} \right)^{1/4} \quad (39)$$

- Velocity scale:

$$u_\eta = (\varepsilon \cdot \vartheta)^{1/4} \quad (40)$$

- Time scale:

$$\tau_\eta = \left(\frac{\vartheta}{\varepsilon} \right)^{1/2} \quad (41)$$

Where the dissipation rate is given by [81]:

$$\varepsilon = \vartheta \cdot \left(\frac{u_\eta}{\eta} \right)^2 = \frac{\vartheta}{\tau_\eta^2} \sim \frac{u_0^3}{\ell_0} \quad (42)$$

With the definition of the smaller scales (equation (39) to (41)) and the largest scale eddies (ℓ_0 , u_0 and τ_0), the characteristic values of these two scales can be correlated to the mean flow Reynolds number [80]:

$$\frac{\eta}{\ell_0} \sim Re^{-3/4} \quad (43)$$

$$\frac{u_\eta}{u_0} \sim Re^{-1/4} \quad (44)$$

$$\frac{\tau_\eta}{\tau_0} \sim Re^{-1/2} \quad (45)$$

Because the ratio η/ℓ_0 decreases with Re , it is easy to conclude that for high Re , there is a range of ℓ that are very small when compared with ℓ_0 , but very high when compared with η . In this range, the Reynolds number is large, and the turbulence does not depend on viscosity. This is known as the inertial subrange (see Figure 31), where:

$$\ell_{DI} < \ell < \ell_{EI} \quad (46)$$

For:

$$\ell_{DI} = 60 \cdot \eta \quad (47)$$

In dissipation range (for $\ell < \ell_{DI}$) viscous effects are strong. Eddies with a length scale larger than ℓ_{EI} , carry most energy, therefore it is called the Energy-container range (see Figure 31) [80].

By calculating the different eddy length scales dimensions for high Re , it is possible to identify the energy cascade –as shown in Figure 32. Where \mathfrak{S} represents the energy rate transferred from higher eddies to smaller ones and \mathcal{P} the rate of production of turbulent kinetic energy [80] defined by:

$$\mathcal{P} = -\langle u_i; u_j \rangle \frac{\partial \langle \bar{u}_i \rangle}{\partial x_j} \quad (48)$$

Figure 32 – A representation of the energy cascade at a very large Reynolds number. [80].

Assuming that L is the characteristic length of large eddies and it can be approached to:

$$L \equiv k^{3/2} / \varepsilon \quad (49)$$

And the turbulence Reynolds number is given by [80]:

$$Re_L \equiv \frac{k^{1/2} \cdot L}{\vartheta} = \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon \cdot \vartheta} \quad (50)$$

Considering a length scale such that $\eta < \lambda_g < L$, the local turbulence Reynolds, based on the Taylor scale [80] is obtained by:

$$Re_\lambda = \left(\frac{20 \cdot Re_L}{3} \right)^{1/2} \equiv \frac{\sqrt{u'^2} \cdot \lambda_g}{\vartheta} \quad (51)$$

The microscale (λ_g) is defined as [80], [81]:

$$\lambda_g = \left(\frac{15 \cdot \vartheta}{\varepsilon} \right)^{1/2} \cdot u' \quad (52)$$

4.2 Computational cost of DNS simulations

The computational cost is the major problem in DNS. Pope [80] proposed a grid spacing (Δx) of [80]:

$$\Delta x \approx \alpha \cdot \eta \quad (53)$$

In equation (53), α is a constant, typically taking a value of 2.1. In some cases, is possible to use $\alpha=3$ or 4, in order to reduce mesh density. For a structured hexahedral grid, the mesh can be aligned with the flow gradient and boundary layers, which can reduce the number of mesh elements [82]. The volume of each grid element can be calculated for an orthogonal mesh as:

$$V_{element} = \Delta x^3 \quad (54)$$

To estimate the number of control volumes constituting the grid (N), it is necessary to know the volume of the flow domain (V_{domain}) such that:

$$N = \frac{V_{domain}}{V_{element}} \quad (55)$$

It should be noted that using symmetry boundary conditions is not recommended to reduce N, since symmetry does not exist in the presence of turbulence [50]. N defines the number of equations that have to be simultaneously solved after numerical discretization thus has a direct influence on the computational time and required memory size. This could lead to problems where the numerical solution becomes impractical or even impossible for existing hardware. Considering a CPU capable of performing one billion floating-point operations per second, in the year 2000, Pope [80] reported a limit for the Re_λ of 100, which corresponds to $N=1.25 \times 10^8$. For 1 Gigaflop computer, the convergence time is expected to be 13 days.

In DNS, reducing the computational cost is equivalent to reducing the number of elements in the grid. For that, there are three possible options:

- Reduce the flow domain volume;
- Reduce the Reynolds number;

- Hybrid solution.

By performing a hybrid simulation, such as LES/DNS or RANS/DNS is an efficient approach, more information about this approach can be found in section 4.3.1. To reduce the Reynolds number, one can reduce the characteristic dimension of the flow channel, i.e. the nozzle throat diameter in case of an ejector. Ejectors can be designed using simple 1D models, such as the one published in [83]. Those models can be easily adapted to consider the maximum elements for the grid available by the computer. For this project, the computer that will be used in the simulation has the power to compute around 8×10^9 grid elements. To adapt the 1D model is necessary to add the equations (39), (42), (53) (using 3 or 4 as α value), and (54). Being the ΔV_{domain} the total ejector volume. The same approach can be applied to a hybrid solution, where ΔV_{domain} is the volume where DNS will be used. Being the scale ejector geometry the output of this 1D model.

To simulate an ejector using DNS, the ejector dimensions should be very small, which have no practical interest, e.g. for a cooling application. Very small ejectors are also difficult to manufacture within the required tolerances. Nevertheless, the results obtained from a DNS simulation would have an important contribution to understanding the expansion/mixing/recompression processes, which are not thoroughly answered by convention simulation methods.

It is important to guarantee that the continuum hypothesis is valid when applying the Navier-Stokes equations. The continuum hypothesis is valid for length scales ranging from 100 nm to 1 μ m for gases and higher than 10 nm for liquids. For scales smaller than these, the continuum hypothesis might not be valid [84]. Another important factor is the ratio between the characteristic length scale (L_{char}) and the mean free path (L_{path}), called the Knudsen number and defined as:

$$Kn = \frac{L_{path}}{L_{char}} \quad (56)$$

The Knudsen number indicated whether the no-slip condition and the continuum hypothesis are valid. The mean free path (L_{path}) is the free length that a molecule must move before shocking with another molecule. The slip boundary condition is assumed when the mean free path compared with the characteristic length of the flow. In general it can be stated that [84]:

- $Kn > 0.1$ – the continuums hypothesis is not valid;
- $0.001 < Kn < 0.1$ - the continuums hypothesis is valid with slip flow boundary condition;
- $Kn < 0.001$ - the continuums hypothesis is valid with no-slip flow boundary condition.

4.3 DNS for supersonic jets

This section presents a brief state of the art regarding DNS for the simulation of supersonic turbulent flows. Early publications applying DNS considered incompressible flows only. The first DNS model published was in 1972 [85]. It had a relatively poor resolution but was the first step to solve isotropic turbulence in a wind tunnel. In 1981, with the improvement of computer speed and capacity, Rogallo [86] applied DNS to simulate homogeneous turbulence in an incompressible flow, using previous work from Orszag and Patterson [85]. Rogallo's work takes into account the mean shear, irrotational strain, and rotation on homogeneous turbulence. The results obtained by both above-mentioned works were the pioneering work for setting the standard homogeneous turbulence in DNS. Only in 1987, the first wall-bounded incompressible homogeneous turbulent flow was computed using DNS [87]. This flow Re was 3 300 (on the centerline) and the numerical grid included about 4 million grid points. The results were compared with pre-existing experimental data. The main difference was in the near-wall region. The authors considered that the observed differences occurred due to the heat-conduction problem by measuring turbulence quantities near the wall [87]. Moin and Spalart [88] published their work about turbulent flow in curved channels. Later, Moin and Kahesh [89], considered wall heat transfer curvature, and riblets. Both works considered homogeneous and incompressible flows.

DNS for compressible turbulent flow simulations started in the early 1980s and took almost 10 years to find significant results [89]. A wall-bounded compressible flow was simulated by Coleman et al. [90] with $Ma=1.5$ and 3 and $Re=3\ 000$ (for the centerline). The findings are consistent with Kim et al. [87] prior's work. When compared with those results, the Ma and Re revealed discrepancies. When incompressible and compressible turbulent flow are compared, the Reynolds shear stress and turbulent heat flux profiles show identical results. The mixing length and the Reynolds shear stress correlation coefficient [87] behave similarly. P. Huang [91] presented DNS simulation results for two compressible flows between isothermal walls under the conditions: 1) $Re=3\ 000$ and $Ma=1.5$ and 2) $Re=4\ 880$ with $Ma=3$. The objective was to study the Reynolds averaged mean flow and turbulent quantities in detail. The computational cost was not mentioned as a problem by the authors.

Another breakthrough was obtained by Vreman et al. [92] by the simulation in a high-speed turbulent mixing layer using DNS. The main goal was to evaluate the mixing layer growth rate in a turbulent flow with the Mach number between 0.2 and 1.2. It was concluded that there was a reduction in the mixing layer growth with the increase in the Mach number, due to the reduction in the pressure-strain term. Mahesh et al. [93] studied the shock-wave influence in an isotropic turbulent flow using DNS. They simulated flows with Mach of 1.29 and 1.8, with shock waves, and microscale Reynolds number (Re_λ) of 19.1 and 19.5, respectively. Each numerical mesh had about 1.5 million grid points.

Freund and Moin [94], applied DNS in a free jet expansion after a nozzle. They validated the results with previous experimental work. It was concluded that a small change in the nozzle diameter is sufficient to induce a significant shift in downstream flow. Freund et al. [95] presented a paper concerning DNS results for a similar jet, but with $Ma=1.92$. The main objective was to study the noise reduction in a low Re supersonic flow. Mean flow characteristics and Reynolds stresses show that the turbulence is realistic and that the statistical sample was large enough to get convergent findings.

The above-mentioned publications report simulation results for low Reynolds number cases. It is important to emphasize that such flows have little practical interest since the Reynolds number in an industrial scale nozzle is considerably higher. A higher Reynolds Number (100 000) case for a cylindrical wall-bounded flow was simulated by Terzi et al. [96] in 2005 with a $Ma=2.46$. The authors used the maximum number of grid points limited by the computer capacity (52 million). The computer had 128 processors with 82.21 MFlops per processor. The simulation took about 280 000 CPU hours (about 3 months). Using a hybrid LES/RANS solution, with $Re=3\ 300\ 000$, the simulation time was reduced to 1 and a half months with the same computer [96]. These results show that computational times can be considerably reduced by applying a hybrid approach even for higher a higher Reynolds number.

Most recent papers reporting DNS results for supersonic jets concern combustion process and heat transfer in jet flames [97]–[99]. DNS solves the species continuity, and chemical reaction kinetics, besides the Navier-Stoke equations. DNS is ideal to apply for supersonic reacting flows [97] such as combustion. Besides, DNS has been used to study jet acoustics. The large eddies are responsible for the jet acoustics, because those are geometry-dependent, LES can be a good approach to simulating the jet acoustics [100].

It can be concluded that the advances in computer power opened up the opportunity to carry out DNS simulations of a variety of turbulent flows. DNS is time-consuming and computationally demanding, therefore their general application is still constrained. Because of that, researchers apply LES instead of DNS as a feasible compromise as the geometrical complexity and Re increases[101]. For more information concerning research application of LES in supersonic and high Reynolds number flows in complex geometries (as nozzles, diffusers, and convergent-divergent) and for two-phase flows, the reader is referred to [9], [102], [103]. Because of the expected advances in information technology and the exponential increase in computational speed, it is expected that DNS and LES simulation could replace conventional experimentation in the next 20 years [104].

4.3.1 Turbulent flow simulation using Hybrid approaches

Hybrid models have been developed to compromise computational effort and information loss. In a hybrid approach, the flow domain is discretized with a fine mesh for the regions where LES or DNS is applied and with a coarser mesh where RANS is used to predict turbulence.

The LES/RANS hybrid scheme has been applied before for the simulation of the flow inside ejectors. Figure 33 shows the schematics of a 3D model where LES was applied at the mixing zone of the ejector and RANS was used for the rest of the flow [48]. The authors claimed that it was possible to obtain a deep understanding of the ejector process at a low computational cost.

Figure 33 – Ejector 3D model identifying the different models applied [48].

In a hybrid model, there are two essential questions to be answered. First what type of turbulence models to apply; and second how to couple them. Besides, it is also important to establish criteria on how to divide the flow domain for the individual model types. Two approaches can be followed for LES/RANS hybrid models [47]:

- Embedded LES (ELES): a given part of the flow domain is solved using LES and the rest using RANS. Usually, LES is applied in the critical area(s) to analyze;
- Bridge the near-wall: the near-wall region is solved with a RANS model and LES is applied for the bulk flow.

Hybrid turbulence models are recent, little work is reported regarding the hybridization of DNS with other approaches [101]. For LES/RANS models, there are a few methodologies for coupling, as presented in Figure 34. Some of these approached could be adopted to DNS/LES or DNS/RANS type of hybrid models. There are two ways to couple LES with RANS: 1) segregated and 2) unified [47]. In the first approach, one part of the computational domain is modeled with RANS and LES is applied to the other. In this approach, RANS and LES calculations are independent and are subsequently connected through internal boundary conditions. This model requires a clear definition of flow regions subjected to RANS or LES, as well as the interface model. This concept is depicted in Figure 35.

Figure 34 – List of different approaches to resolving eddies in turbulent flows (adapted from [47]).

Figure 35 – Possible interface between hybrid LES/RANS simulation for segregated modeling - Embedded LES [47].

The characteristics of the interface between LES/RANS using the segregated approach can be summarized as follows [47]:

- In the inflow coupling, the mean values from RANS are transported into the LES substructure. Instabilities in the RANS part can interfere with the LES domain. To avoid the creation of an artificial boundary layer in the LES sub-grid, it is necessary to know the flow fluctuations at the interface.
- Outflow coupling is when the RANS zone is downstream of the LES. Thin this case, LES needs to supply RANS with mean flow information.
- Tangential coupling is needed when the mean flow streamlines from RANS and LES are aligned. Tangential coupling is not well reported [47], [105], it is still a challenge for future research. With RANS, only mean flow properties are computed, thus the interface of the solution becomes discontinuous. The possible solution is to treat the flow as a multi-domain problem. For more information about this strategy, the reader is referred to [105].

The unified modeling is ideal for coupling the LES/RANS type interface since LES models have similarities with RANS. The available methods for indicated in Figure 35.

Layering, or a two-layer model, is a method that can be applied in steady-state (hard interface) or transient (soft interface) simulations. In the two-layer approach, RANS is applied near the walls, while LES is used further away from the solid surfaces [47]. Figure 36 shows the instantaneous velocity contours in a flow with a sudden expansion using a hybrid model (LES/RANS) with a soft layering interface (black line). One may note that the interface position varies along the flow direction. Further details about this model can be found in [47].

Figure 36 – Instantaneous velocity using a hybrid LES/RANS model with a soft two-layer interface [47].

The “limited” method was obtained through the renormalization group theory. It assumes that the eddy viscosity is the same at the LES/RANS interface such [47]:

$$\vartheta_t^{RANS} = C_\mu \cdot \frac{k^{3/2}}{\varepsilon} \quad (57)$$

$$\vartheta_t^{LES} = C_\mu \cdot \varepsilon_\tau^{1/3} \cdot \Delta x^{4/3} \quad (58)$$

The “weighted average” method (see Fig.35) is the simple way to couple two different models. As the name suggests, any quantity (Φ) can be calculated by a weighted average of:

$$\Phi^{hybrid} = f \cdot \Phi^{RANS} + (1 - f) \cdot \Phi^{LES}, \text{ with } 0 \leq f \leq 1 \quad (59)$$

Where f is called the blending factor and it is an empirical function of time and space [47].

The “damping” approach, also known as Flow Simulation Method (FSM), redefined the turbulent stress in equation (15) as:

$$\tau_{ij}^{FSM} = f_{\Delta x} \left(\frac{\Delta x}{\ell_K} \right) \cdot \tau_{ij}^{RANS}, \text{ with } 0 \leq f_{\Delta x} \leq 1 \quad (60)$$

In equation (60) Δx is the grid size and ℓ_K can be approximated from the Kolmogorov length scale (equation (39)). $f_{\Delta x}$ is a contribution function that approaches RANS for a coarse grid and DNS for a finer mesh (grid size equal to Kolmogorov length scale) [47]. The contribution function can be computed by [47]:

$$f_{\Delta x} \left(\frac{\Delta x}{\ell_K} \right) = (1 - e^{-\beta \cdot \Delta x / \ell_K})^n \quad (61)$$

The exponent n controls the steepness of the function and β is called the model contribution resolution level. It is important to note that f_{Δ} varies in space and time. This enables the use of RANS, LES, and DNS in the same model, depending on the grid size (Δx) [47].

It is important to select the most appropriate interface model for a given problem since it is a critical issue in hybrid simulations. The incorrect selection can create regions that induce unwanted errors in the results [101]. The grid size is also another important factor to ensure accuracy. A seamless and regulated transition from RANS to LES is essential.

Analyzing the literature revealed that there is a lack of DNS applications to complex flow problems, such as ejectors, despite the interest. This is mostly imposed by current computing power. Most flows of interests in engineering and nature are highly turbulent with a high degree of unknowns in the eyes of science. Research is needed to find and developed new methods to simulate relevant cases for engineering applications, such as ejector flow, which would otherwise be nearly impossible by conventional experimentation. LES is a good candidate, however, this method could be insufficient to describe flow fields with considerable random variabilities.

Due to hardware constraints, hybrid simulation appears like an excellent compromise between computational cost and accuracy. DNS hybridization has not been reported yet in the literature. The main goal of the proposed Ph.D. work is to develop such a model for ejector simulation for the first time.

5 Identification of the research objectives

5.1 Research objectives

The main focus and principal novelty of the doctoral work are to develop a Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) model for the fundamental study of the flow phenomena in supersonic variable geometric ejectors (VGE). DNS will be developed for the entire ejector or the mixing process, depending on the computational demand. In this latter case, a hybridized modeling approach will be proposed. The operational conditions to be considered will be suitable for both sub-critical refrigeration cycles (single-phase ejectors) and trans-critical (two-phase ejectors), driven by a renewable energy source. Another objective of the proposed work is the validation of the model developed with existing prototypes and through experimental testing. The experimental setup will be constructed at INEGI if founding is obtained through national project calls. Otherwise, an existing test rig will be used in international collaboration. The results obtained will contribute to a better understanding of the complex flow phenomena inside ejectors involving supersonic expansion and mixing, phase change, shock trains, and other relevant processes. The work will contribute to identifying the limitations of traditional RANS-based CFD models and to the geometric optimization of the VGE. It is expected that the overall performance of the ejector will be improved, especially under variable operating conditions - which is expected to occur in refrigeration systems and heat pumps, powered by renewable energy sources (such as solar panels, thermal or photovoltaic). It will also be an objective to compare the performance of these cycles with other existing cycles (compression, adsorption, and absorption).

5.2 Proposed work plan

The proposed work is divided into five parts as presented in Figure 37, and in two major writing documents (seminar and final thesis).

Figure 37 – Structure of the proposed work plan.

1. Literature research and study of the state of art

The first step of the work was the comprehensive literature review. This part of the study resulted partially in the present seminar work. The objective was to carry out a systematic literature review on the application of ejectors in refrigeration cycles and heat pumps. The existing types of ejectors and their expected performance were addressed. A critical literature review was conducted on the existing mathematical models to simulate the flow of subcritical and transcritical ejectors, analyzing their values and limitations previous work on supersonic jets using the DNS technique was also reviewed.

2. Design of a subcritical and a transcritical ejector using 1D models and RANS CFD simulations

In the second part of the work, the preliminary design of 2 variable geometry ejectors will be achieved by applying simple 1D models, one for a subcritical refrigeration cycle (with R1234ze(E)) and another one for a transcritical heat pump with CO₂ working fluid. In the first ejector, the flow is expected to be in the vapor phase, while in the second ejector phase change will occur. In both cases, the design working conditions will be suitable for solar-powered systems.

The final geometry of the ejectors will be refined using CFD applying conventional RANS turbulence models. These models will be used for the determination of the complete operation maps of the designed ejectors.

3. DNS modeling and model hybridization

A DNS model will be developed for the scale ejector previously designed. The computational time will be estimated. If needed ejector scaling will be performed or a hybridization approach will be followed by keeping the DNS model to study the mixing process, being the most important process in the ejector affecting entrainment.

The effect of the computational mesh on the distribution of flow variables (such as pressure) will be studied along the length of the ejector. The results will be compared with the CFD results using the RANS models. The shock wave structures in the ejector will be evaluated and the isentropic efficiencies will be estimated, to optimize the mixture of the supersonic jets and improve the ejector performance.

4. Experimental setup

An experimental study of the flow inside the ejector will be carried out. A test rig will be constructed to visualize the flow inside the ejector. The goal is to do the experimental characterization of the jet mixing processes and the shock wave structure inside the ejector. The ejector will use air as the working fluid. The pressure distribution along the ejector will also be measured to validate the numerical models. In case of a lack of financing to construct the experimental installation, the tests will be performed on an existing test rig under the international collaboration. Additional tests will be carried out

to measure the global performance indicators with the existing solar energy-driven ejector cooling cycle, using R600a as the working fluid.

5. Model validation

In the final part of the proposed Ph.D. work, the experimental results will be used to validate the developed DNS and RANS models. The validated models can be later used to optimize the geometry of VGE's. A comparison will also be made of the performance of the ejection cycles with equivalent absorption cycles for the subcritical cooling system and with conventional CO₂ heat pumps for the transcritical system.

The above study will be documented in a Ph.D. dissertation.

5.3 Expected outcomes of the thesis

For this work, there are several expected outcomes. First of all, this document (seminar) and the Ph.D. thesis. Besides, the other outputs are:

- Three scientific papers and three conference proceedings;
- One experimental setup;
- Several mathematical models.

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